

ACADEMIC STRESS IN THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON STUDENTS' PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

Ihomjonova Dilnoza San'antjon qizi

Namazbaeva Asemgul Erbol qizi

Students of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

dee4nluv@gmail.com

aseamanamazbaeva8@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor: Masharipov Yunus Akhmed ug'li

ESL teacher of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Abstract. Academic stress become a serious problem in modern educational system. It affects students' psychological well-being, motivation and their academic performance. This article is about nature, sources and consequences of academic stress drawing on 3 key sources: systematical research of Fomina, Fillipova and Morosanova (2025), published in journal *New ideas in child and educational Psychology*; longitudinal research of study effects and psychological outcomes during the adolescence by Roeser, Eccles and Sameroff (1998), also modern analysis of institutional support published UNIRANKS (2025). They explore how chronic academic pressure lead to anxiety, burnout, social isolation and low motivation. Moreover, it research institutional strategies based on evidence that the Universities can implement to address these challenges. The findings underscore the urgent need of psychological support systems, flexible academic policies and school environments that nurtures students competence, responsibility and belonging.

Key words: academic stress, psychological well-being, School environment, burnout, motivation, institutional support, responsibility

Introduction

One of the most crucial facilities in a person's life is education, that impacts both intellectual development and emotional and physical functioning. Throughout their lives, humanity strives to improve and discover new horizons of exploration. Thus, the pressure required from students at all levels of education have rose considerably in a past few decades, leading to the emergence of what scientists now define as both a distinct and broader phenomenon: educational stress. Unlike general life stress, educational pressure results from high demands on students, as well as psychological and individual resources.

Formative durable study by Roeser, Eccles, and Sameroff (1998) figured out that the school learning environment has a significant impact on the academic motivation and emotional well-being of adolescents. The scientists' research of over 1000 students in secondary schools demonstrated that students' recognitions of educational materials, along with teacher support, the quality of relationship between students and teachers, and perceived autonomy are crucial features of both motivational engagement and psychological health outputs in process of time. The latest UNIRANKS report of well-being (2025) found a route of rising nervousness, fatigue, and social isolation among university students, calling on institutions to establish a more supportive learning environment for students.

This article discusses data from these three sources: 1) the occurrence and nature of educational stress; 2) the consequences for education and psychological health; 3) institutional strategies that are capable to help mitigate stress in educational setting. These

analysis are particularly given to the point proceeding rise in mental health disorders among students, which is exactly influences their quality of life, scholarly results, and future career route.

Methodology

This article is qualitative that based on literature design research. Content analysis was applied to three primary sources that cover different but complementary perspectives on academic stress. First source is systematically review of Fomina, Fillipova, Morosanova (2025), which analyze the articles from Google scholar, science direct, PubMed and research gate with use of keywords: "Educational stress", "Academic stress", "Student well-being" and "Stress management". Second source is Roeser, Eccles and Sameroff, which tracked 1041 adolescents during the Middle School using both methods: variable centered and person-centered to study the relationship between school environment perception, motivation and emotional function. Third source is contemporary analytical report of UNIRANKS (2025), addressed to practical institutional responses to grow academic stress in University settings. Next, data that obtained from all resources were thematically triangulated for getting shared patterns across distinct academic levels and national context. The central themes that emerged in process of analyze: reason of stress, psychological consequences and institutional responses create organizational backbone of the discussion part below.

Discussion

Nature and Sources of Academic Stress

Educational stress is observed as a psychological phenomenon and a persistent state of tension caused by students in response to factors particular to the academic process. According to the confirming Fomina et al. (2025) that the principal cause of the academic burnout revealed through a lack of students' internal capacity, both emotional and cognitive resources. The studies highlight several key sources of stress, including preparation for examinations, worrying about academic performance, competitive assessment systems, heavy workloads, fear of failure, limited time to complete tasks, and challenges in communication with teachers and peers.

According to Roeser, Eccles, and Sameroff (1998), using durable studies, demonstrated that the teaching environment itself may function either as a major source of stress or as a protective feature. Students who viewed their school like supportive environment to study, promoting competence, and a sense of belonging tended to display stronger educational motivation and healthier emotional adjustment in process of time. On the other hand, those who observed their school like a unsupportive educational atmosphere, highly competitive through academic process, or unfeeling to their personal needs showed greater level of depression symptoms and lack of interest in educational environment among seventh and eighth classes. This phenomenon demonstrates that academic stress is effected both by individual, institutional and interpersonal conditions.

The report in an article UNIRANKS (2025) assists this belief by determining modern pressure modifying university students, such as intense academic workload, anxiety of failing their examinations, issues with budget, and maintain stability in studies both in social and personal obligations. In general sense, in these articles identifying that educational stress may occur in both personal and interpersonal features. And tackle this issue the most effective solution can be complex and multifaceted.

Consequences for psychological well being and academic performance

Academic stress affect wide range of negative consequences to mental and physical health of students. Fomina et al 2025 identify multiple negative impact to psychological well-

being included high level of anxiety, depression, decrease life satisfaction and worsen cognitive function. However, authors highlight the relationship between stress and academic performance are not only negative: moderate stress can have mobilizing effect, and that increase temporary concentration and attention. Chronic and excessive stress sometimes undermines performance, decreased creativity and destroy motivation. Longitudinal information of Roeser et al (1998) confirm face patterns on youth: student low motivation and elevated depression which high percentage maintain or worsen this profile. Especially when there was no school support. Nevertheless, there is one more research that demonstrates: if the motivation is low emotional condition will be also low that lead to non-interested to study.

In physical level according to Union ranks 2025, prolonged academic stress can be the reason of worse condition of sleep, weakness of immune system and chronic fatigue. In society students refuse to speak with their peers because of the pressure. Then they lose their support that could be their protection.

Institutional Strategies and Psychological Studies

All 3 sources are similar with each other in opinions that make it effective support to students as structural and related to relationship. Fomina et al (2025) devote particular attention to the role of self-regulation as key resource - opportunity of follow their cognitive and emotional process, also said realistic goals and manage with their effort. According to the author development of these skills must be the main goal of psychological support in education.

Roeser et al (1998) similarly points to the school environment itself as a critical resource. It supports who is responsibility and have good relationship with their teachers and students, demonstrating the best motivational and emotional results. UNIRANKS (2025) add some practical support: available consultation service, flexible deadline for students in critical situation, programs that support equal trainings of stress management.

Conclusion

Academic stress is structural embedded phenomenon that affects from middle school to universities. This article has shown that its sources not only related to individuality but also how educational environment satisfy basic need of adolescents incompetence, responsibility and belonging. Consequences - from anxiety and depression till diminished maturation and social isolation are serious and well documented.

Findings show double responsibility. On the one hand, students need support in improving psychological resources, especially, self-regulation skills. On the other hand, educational centers must recheck all requests and quality of support. Supportive relationship, educational programs that available for mental health and flexible policies - it is not peripheral fulfil but fundamental conditions for effective learning.

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